

#MahsaAmini: Iranian Twitter Activism in Times of Computational Propaganda

Hossein Kermani

Political Communication Group, University of Vienna

Abstract

This paper discusses how the recent hybrid movement in Iran, #MahsaAmini, is taking Twitter activism into the post-fake news era. I will begin by reviewing the existing literature on Twitter and democracy. Then, using the #MahsaAmini protests as an example, I will show how Iranians have circumvented the regime's fake news campaigns and cyber army. This paper argues that while non-democratic regimes have developed more complex methods of suppressing digital protests, these efforts are ineffective in large-scale protests.

Keywords: Twitter activism, #MahsaAmini, Iran, digital democracy, hashtag activism.

Introduction

As many studies show, Twitter has become a central platform for political communication nowadays. Since the 2009 presidential election in Iran, the Green Movement, the Arab Spring, and the #occupy movement, Twitter has been widely used in political protests and elections around the globe. Yet several studies have cast doubt on the effectiveness of Twitter activism, calling it slacktivism or clicktivism. This criticism was amplified when non-democratic regimes employed more complicated co-optation strategies in crushing Twitter protests, such as spreading false information. As a result, some studies have argued that Twitter is no longer an influential tool for democratic movements.

In this paper, I discuss how the recent hybrid #MahsaAmini movement challenges such claims, as Iranian users resisted the regime's manipulative campaigns. This paper provides preliminary observations on the changing manipulative strategies of the Iranian cyber army. Moreover, I discuss how such strategies failed to influence Persian Twitter (Iranian Twittersphere).

Three lines of literature on Twitter and democracy

There are three main directions of studies on Twitter and democracy, especially focusing on political protests in non-democratic regimes. Early studies of how people on the margins of society use this social platform focused on Twitter's role in initiating, developing, and transmitting political upheaval against tyrannies. The Green Movement in Iran in 2009 and the Arab Spring protests provided the impetus for this series of studies. In these early cases, local citizens discovered the promising potential of Twitter (and other social media) to mobilize protests, coordinate their actions, spread the movement, seek solidarity, and forge linkage between local and international protesters (Howard & Hussain, 2013; Papacharissi & De Fatima Oliveira, 2012; Tufekci, 2017; Wojcieszak & Smith, 2013). Later, such movements inspired protests against the injustice of governments in democratic societies, such as the #occupy

movement in the United States (Penney & Dadas, 2014) and the 15-M movement (#15M) in Spain (González-Bailón, 2015). These movements mostly aimed to overthrow political regimes and challenge the hard core of power. Although these movements were shaped in social media, they also unfolded offline in the streets (Poell & van Dijck, 2018). Castells (2013) explains what constitutes the identity of these movements with the notion of a "culture of sharing" and emphasizes the importance of sharing practices that distinguish them from offline movements. Following this logic, scholars have referred to this new type of protest as hashtag activism. Among many similarities, recent hashtag movements, e.g., #MeToo, differ from earlier cases in some ways. Hashtag activism focuses primarily on how minor and peripheral groups in democratic countries use Twitter to challenge racial, gender, and other forms of systematic violence and inequality. In doing so, it is not necessarily the government that is being criticized. All forces that underpin any form of injustice and inequality are being challenged (e.g., the police). Hashtag activism, then, refers to the act of fighting for or supporting a cause using hashtags as the primary channel to raise awareness of an issue and promote debate on social media (Tomblinson & Wolf, 2017). More importantly, hashtag activism is relatively carried out through linguistic actions (e.g., discursive practices) and thus less dependent on offline protests on the ground. This fact, independent of the hashtag protests that unfold in streets and squares such as #Blacklivesmatter, has led to several critiques.

Hashtag activism is criticized for not being "real" activism or as "slacktivism," as it does not animate physical bodies and does not inspire people to take concrete action (Barker-Plummer & Barker-Plummer, 2017; Myles, 2019; Shaw, 2016). In this mode of thinking, digitally mediated discourse is viewed as a cultural resource that can later be mobilized for offline political action (Polletta, 2006).

The second line of research began with responses to these criticisms. This wave focuses on the discursive power of hashtags and argues that digital discourse is inherently political, with or without subsequent street demonstrations. Shaw (2012) draws on Young (1997) to understand hashtag activism as 'discursive activism,' which she defines as "speech or texts that seek to challenge opposing discourses by exposing power relations within these discourses, denaturalizing what appears natural, and demonstrating the flawed assumptions and situatedness of mainstream social discourse." (p. 42). Discursive activism does not necessarily aim to subvert political systems by bringing people to the streets but to critique dominant discourses and narratives that underpin inequality in society. Similarly, Clark (2016) argues that hashtag feminism, as a form of hashtag activism, is a contested performance through which activists make the personal political, bridge the individual and the collective to speak out against sexual violence, and highlight the systemic nature of social injustice.

That said, as ordinary citizens used social media to challenge non-democratic regimes, regimes also developed various tactics to dismantle these platforms. Using a set of strategies that Gunitsky (2015) refers to as "negative control," authoritarian regimes enforced digital censorship, surveillance and control, and the restriction or disruption of the Internet. Gunitsky (2015) argued that authoritarian regimes have moved from such control and repression strategies to more proactive co-optation tactics. He discussed countermobilization, discourse

framing, preference divulgence, and elite coordination as how social media is repressed to serve regime interests.

The third line of research focuses on computational propaganda. Computational propaganda is defined as "the assemblage of social media platforms, autonomous agents, and big data tasked with the manipulation of public opinion" (Woolley & Howard, 2016, p. 4886). This line of research focuses specifically on the ways that false information, i.e., misinformation/disinformation, is spread via social media. Researchers emphasize that fake news poses a serious threat to social media activism (Abu Arqoub et al., 2020; Dehghan & Glazunova, 2021). Non-democratic regimes and far-right groups and parties in democracies use their cyber armies, including human agents and bot accounts, to spread misinformation and fake news so that users cannot tell what is true and what is not (Duan et al., 2022; Neyazi, 2020). It is a tactic to turn Twitter and other social platforms into a banal medium and corrupt them from within.

Because computational propaganda poses a serious threat to the democratic potential of social media (Keller & Klinger, 2019), and given the large scale of bots and misinformation campaigns on such platforms, researchers have raised serious concerns about whether social media is still effective in underpinning and supporting democratic practices (Agarwal et al., 2022; Boukes & Hameleers, 2022; Brown, 2018). Several cases support these concerns, e.g., the 2016 U.S. presidential election and the Brexit referendum (Bastos & Mercea, 2019; Howard et al., 2018). Nevertheless, I argue that the recent #MahsaAmini movement in Iran shows that Twitter can still play a significant role in democratic movements, especially in a country where it is blocked.

Twitter in Iran: from #WhereIsMyVote to #MahsaAmini

Twitter was blocked in Iran during the 2009 presidential election and subsequent protests known as the Green Movement. At the time, Iranians dominated Twitter with #WhereIsMyVote, a hashtag that became a rallying cry for protesters. This was the first time Twitter played an important role in Iranian politics. But the Iranian regime quickly responded by blocking the social network, which has remained blocked ever since. Despite the regime's suppressive measures, Iranian users have continued to use Twitter to this day through circumvention tools like VPNs and proxy servers. The popularity and importance of Twitter in Iran are because Twitter provides dissidents in Iran, who have traditionally been denied access to mainstream media, a space to share their self-created content with other networks (Khazraee, 2019; Marchant et al., 2018). Since 2009, Twitter has played an important role in many political events in Iran, from elections to sociopolitical protests (Kermani & Tafreshi, 2022; Khazraee, 2019).

At the time of writing this essay (September 28, 2022), the largest Twitter movement in Iran's history is taking place. #MahsaAmini was launched to protest the brutality of Iran's morality police, who reportedly killed a young 22-year-old girl in custody. Police arrested Mahsa Amini for violating the obligation to wear the hijab. The media reported that she was beaten and hospitalized with severe brain damage, while Iranian authorities denied these claims. She died on September 16, 2022. This incident sent the country into a state of shock, and many people

began to show their outrage in the streets and also on Twitter. #MahsaAminni quickly became a huge protest against the regime, and many people took to the streets in many cities across Iran. Now #MahsaAminni has set a Twitter record with more than 130 million tweets and counting. Many Iranian and non-Iranian users use #MahsaAminni to protest against unjust rules and various types of discrimination and repression against Iranians and organize and coordinate street demonstrations.

On the other hand, the Iranian regime has developed several tactics in recent years to dominate Twitter and turn it into a platform loyal to the regime or at least neutral. In addition to many Iranian authorities who manage their accounts on Twitter, such as the supreme leader, the president, and members of parliament, many supporters of the regime, have also joined this platform in recent years (Azadi & Mesgaran, 2021; Kermani & Tafreshi, 2022). Of course, the majority of them belong to the so-called cyber army. Iranian officials have confirmed that they operate their cyber army through Twitter. For example, Hossein Salami, the commander-in-chief of the Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps (IRGC), said that they have two thousand cyber battalions. These battalions work to fight the regime's enemies and dominate cyberspace in favor of the regime. These cyber agents, officially managed and funded by the regime, are particularly active in #MahsaAminni. As described in the literature section, the main focus of such cyber armies and coordinated actions is to manipulate social media and silence dissidents using various strategies.

I focus on the #MahsaAminni case to examine what techniques were used by the Iranian cyber army and whether or not they were successful in suppressing this movement.

#MahsaAminni as a hybrid movement: toward the post-misinformation era

I have been monitoring Persian Twitter since April 1, 2022. On a daily basis, I have collected the most popular posts that had more than 1,000 likes per day and analyzed them in terms of the content and discourses they sought to produce, challenge, or dominate. In addition, I have analyzed how users loyal to the regime, known as Arzeshi, attempted to manipulate the flow of discussion on Twitter. This longitudinal analysis has allowed me to analyze how the cyber army changed its tactics in the early stages of #MahsaAminni and during its peak (until today).

Although systematic analysis of this data requires more time, I present some of my initial findings to provide more insight into this unfolding movement and how the case of #MahsaAminni could contribute to the existing literature on Twitter activism.

First, I argue that #MahsaAminni is a hybrid movement. It is not limited to Twitter alone. It has characteristics of both early Twitter protests and more recent, more text-based hashtag movements. Like early 'Twitter revolutions,' #MahsaAminni relies heavily on street demonstrations and aims to overthrow Iran's political system. Street demonstrations and Twitter activism are mutually reinforcing in this case. Moreover, #MahsaAminni is a powerful discursive attempt to challenge some of the regime's hegemonic discourse nodal points, such as the hijab. In fact, the campaign was launched in protest against forced veiling. Users shared many photos of women and girls walking through cities without hijabs and women cutting

their hair in solidarity with other women. The tweet below from a leading account illustrates one of them:

Fig. 1: Women are walking without hijab in Iran

Unlike previous movements against the hijab, such as #tajavoz (in Persian: تجاوز), which is known as the Iranian #MeToo and I will come back to it later, the #MahsaAminni movement combines offline protests with discursive transmissions. Through their online presence, women have started to reclaim their bodies and demand their rights in public spaces, which was not new. Nevertheless, their efforts were supported by street demonstrations this time.

Second, the #MahsaAminni movement demonstrates that hashtag movements that are not accompanied by street demonstrations are not meaningless. They are effective in generating discontent and awareness, which at the time could lead to large hybrid movements. In fact, #MahsaAmini is a gateway through which the pent-up energy accumulated by other hashtags in recent years has been flushed onto Iranian streets. For example, #dont_execute was another hashtag activism Iranians initiated to stop the regime from executing prisoners, especially political prisoners. Similarly, #buy_vaccine was another attempt to persuade Iranian authorities to import effective vaccines during the Covid-19 crisis. One of the most notable cases was #rape, i.e., the Iranian equivalent of #metoo, as a protest against discrimination against women, sexual harassment, and violence. None of these hashtags sparked street demonstrations or even led to tangible results.

An important finding, however, is that the regime's efforts to spread misinformation during the #MahsaAminni movement were not effective. My initial findings suggest that prior to the movement, the cyber army had managed to dominate the Twittersphere to some degree. But at the time of such a large anti-regime movement, their efforts to manipulate discussions failed. I identified eight tactics used by the cyber army: Downgrading discussions to the level of the government, justifying the state's policies, cheering up other users, portraying that everything is

normal, redirecting debates, spreading fake news, trending misleading hashtags, and mocking dissidents and activists.

In Iran's political system, there is a difference between the state and the government. In short, the state refers to the entirety of the regime, which consists mainly of the leader and his trusted individuals and organizations, such as the Guardian Council. The state is led by the Supreme Leader, now Ali Khamenei. As head of government, the president is elected by the people, but elections in Iran are not completely free. The people must choose their candidate from a limited list approved by the Guardian Council (the leader appoints the members of this council). Here, regime supporters seek to shift responsibility for failures to the government and exonerate the leader and his appointees. Because Persian Twitter has historically been a venue for users critical of the regime to criticize the state, the cyber army sought to downgrade anti-regime discussions to the level of the government. Such tactics were prevalent before the #MahsaAminni movement. However, the tactics changed as the #MahsaAminni movement grew steadily and became larger.

The figure below shows how the tactics of the cyber army changed from April to today. I should mention that these findings are not yet systematically completed and need to be validated by further research.

Fig. 2: The timeline of the rise and fall of the cyber army's practices

As Fig. 2 shows, the main efforts of the cyber army during the movement focused on spreading fake news and misleading hashtags. Let us take the case of the letter ع as an example. The letter ع , pronounced as the English (i) as in "machine," is a common letter in Persian and Arabic languages. This letter is the last word of Amini in Persian. The cyber army took this fact as an opportunity to produce an identical hashtag with a slight difference. They replaced the Persian ع with its Arabic counterpart. Since they were coded differently, the algorithms identified them as two different hashtags. This resulted in many of the Iranian-language hashtag of #Amini being replaced by the Arabic version. Both hashtags look identical but, in fact, are different

because they are coded differently. The result was that some users tweeted about Amini with Arabic hashtags, not realizing that they were duped by the cyber army.

The pro-regime cyber army also spread a large amount of false information. These tactics were mainly used to change the facts and anti-regime narratives, to scare dissidents (spreading fake news about the number of casualties, the power of the armed forces, etc.), to stir up religious sentiments, and to urge people to destroy and burn down certain buildings (mostly residential houses). The last two points could have provided the regime with ammunition to suppress the movement with more violence.

Although such manipulative tactics were not new in hashtag movements, the reaction of Iranian users was highly indicative. They were keen to identify misleading hashtags and fake news. They cited many examples of such messages and urged other users not to be duped by the cyber army. It also happened with the misleading hashtags. For example, Hichkas, a famous Iranian rapper, targeted Twitter, its CEO, and others in a tweet: The Islamic Republic's cyber army is using all its power to create fake hashtags to silence Iranians on Twitter

@OmidKordestani @jack @Twitter @TwitterSuppor. Another user tweeted, " I have yet to see such solidarity! Any fake news is quickly exposed; keep it up, folks!"

Iranians were also quick to respond to misleading information inadvertently spread by the mainstream media. Elon Musk announced in a tweet that he would ask the U.S. government to lift sanctions so he could provide Starlink Internet to Iranians. This was in response to the regime's internet block. Immediately after his tweet, several Iranian foreign journalists, e.g., Fardad Farahzad, and media outlets such as Persian Independent circulated tweets proclaiming that people in Iran were using Starlink. However, this was false. Ordinary citizens responded to such tweets and clarified their mistakes.

It should be mentioned that there are watchdog users on Persian Twitter who have tried to identify and expose cyber army users and tactics even before the movement. Such efforts likely play a role in raising awareness and sensitizing other users.

Given such enlightening efforts by Iranian users, it can be argued that Twitter could still play an important role in amplifying and strengthening political protests. While it is true that there is manipulation and disruption, Iranian users have shown that they have moved beyond the era of fake news and have entered a new phase of hybrid movements. The spread of fake news could be effective to some extent if there were no nationwide hybrid protests in the country, but such efforts clearly failed when large-scale upheaval occurred. #MahsaAminni is a return to the days of powerful hashtag movements supported by large crowds in the streets. It also shows that even heavy investment in manipulating and degrading social platforms can fail. Therefore, I can argue that social media, especially Twitter, has not necessarily become irrelevant in anchoring democratic movements through computational propaganda and suppression.

Conclusion

#MahsaAminni is an unfolding and fast-changing movement. It is happening right now, and we do not know what the outcome and impact will be. It has several different manifestations and different dimensions. In this essay, I focused on how this movement is reviving powerful hybrid movements that challenge dictatorships, as was the case with the Arab Spring. In

addition, I discussed how this case shows that tech-savvy Iranian users are already past digital propaganda. My aim here was not to overstate the impact of technology on social movements; rather, it was to show how an emerging movement in Iran is using new technologies like Twitter as a tool for freedom of speech and political mobilization. It is also a reminder that dictatorships are very aware of the power of social media and try to crack down on it. The fact that Iranians continue to use Twitter despite these efforts shows how important this tool is for democratic movements.

Social media such as Twitter is the only way for people living in non-democratic regimes such as Iran to raise their voices and engage in anti-regime discourse. Yet such media are severely restricted in these contexts, where people need them more than in other countries. Not only is Twitter well protected and freer in Western countries, but the main strand of research focuses on Western democracies. These concerns should be taken into account if we want to help people seek their freedom through social media.

In addition, the #MahsaAmini case and other cases around the world have brought the issue of platform suppression into the spotlight. Several users, including Iranian-American actress Nazanin Nour and famous Iranian musician Keyhan Kalhor, announced that Instagram deleted their posts in solidarity with Iranians. Other users mentioned that Whatsapp, a Meta-owned messaging app, has restricted Iranians' access, probably at the regime's request. As scholars such as Gillespie (2015, 2018) and Tufeksi (2015) have pointed out, platform suppression is a real threat to the success of social media protests. More academic and general efforts are needed to make these platforms more accountable for supporting, not suppressing, democratic movements. This is also a direction for further research on the #MahsaAmini movement that can help other movements succeed in the future.

References

- Abu Arqoub, O., Elegy, A. A., Efe Özad, B., Dwikat, H., & Oloyede, F. A. (2020). Mapping the Scholarship of Fake News Research: A Systematic Review. *Journalism Practice*, 1-31.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17512786.2020.1805791>
- Agarwal, B., Agarwal, A., Harjule, P., & Rahman, A. (2022). Understanding the intent behind sharing misinformation on social media. *Journal of Experimental & Theoretical Artificial Intelligence*, 0(0), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0952813X.2021.1960637>
- Azadi, P., & Mesgaran, M. B. (2021). *The Clash of Ideologies on Persian Twitter* (Issue 10). University of Stanford.
- Barker-Plummer, B., & Barker-Plummer, D. (2017). Twitter as a Feminist Resource: #YesAllWomen, Digital Platforms, and Discursive Social Change. In *Social Movements*

and Media (pp. 91–118). Emerald Insight. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2050-206020170000014010>

Bastos, M. T., & Mercea, D. (2019). The Brexit Botnet and User-Generated Hyperpartisan News. *Social Science Computer Review*, 37(1), 38–54. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894439317734157>

Boukes, M., & Hameleers, M. (2022). Fighting lies with facts or humor: Comparing the effectiveness of satirical and regular fact-checks in response to misinformation and disinformation. *Communication Monographs*, 0(0), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03637751.2022.2097284>

Brown, É. (2018). Propaganda, Misinformation, and the Epistemic Value of Democracy. *Critical Review*, 30(3–4), 194–218. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08913811.2018.1575007>

Castells, M. (2013). *Networks of Outrage and Hope: Social Movements in the Internet Age*. Wiley.

Clark, R. (2016). “Hope in a hashtag”: The discursive activism of #WhyIStayed. *Feminist Media Studies*, 16(5), 788–804. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14680777.2016.1138235>

Dehghan, E., & Glazunova, S. (2021). ‘Fake news’ Discourses. *Journal of Language and Politics*. <https://doi.org/10.1075/jlp.21032.deh>

Duan, Z., Li, J., Lukito, J., Yang, K.-C., Chen, F., Shah, D. V., & Yang, S. (2022). Algorithmic Agents in the Hybrid Media System: Social Bots, Selective Amplification, and Partisan News about COVID-19. *Human Communication Research*, 48(3), 516–542. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hcr/hqac012>

Gillespie, T. (2015). Platforms Intervene. *Social Media + Society*, 1(1), 205630511558047. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2056305115580479>

Gillespie, T. (2018). *CUSTODIANS OF THE INTERNET: PLATFORMS, CONTENT MODERATION, AND THE HIDDEN DECISIONS THAT SHAPE SOCIAL MEDIA*. Yale University Press.

- González-Bailón, S. (2015). Social Protest and New Media. In *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences* (pp. 512–517). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.95076-1>
- Gunitsky, S. (2015). Corrupting the Cyber-Commons: Social Media as a Tool of Autocratic Stability. *Perspectives on Politics*, 13(1), 42–54.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S1537592714003120>
- Howard, P. N., & Hussain, M. M. (2013). *Democracy's Fourth Wave? Digital Media and the Arab Spring*. Oxford University Press.
- Howard, P. N., Woolley, S., & Calo, R. (2018). Algorithms, bots, and political communication in the US 2016 election: The challenge of automated political communication for election law and administration. *Journal of Information Technology & Politics*, 15(2), 81–93.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/19331681.2018.1448735>
- Keller, T. R., & Klinger, U. (2019). Social Bots in Election Campaigns: Theoretical, Empirical, and Methodological Implications. *Political Communication*, 36(1), 171–189.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10584609.2018.1526238>
- Kermani, H., & Tafreshi, A. (2022). Walking with Bourdieu into Twitter communities: An analysis of networked publics struggling on power in Iranian Twittersphere. *Information, Communication & Society*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2021.2021267>
- Khazraee, E. (2019). Mapping the political landscape of Persian Twitter: The case of 2013 presidential election. *Big Data & Society*, 6(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951719835232>
- Marchant, J., Ormson, T., Honari, A., & Sabeti, A. (2018). #iranvotes2017: Analysing the 2017 iranian presidential elections through Telegram, Twitter and Instagram (p. 59). Small Media.

- Myles, D. (2019). 'Anne goes rogue for abortion rights!': Hashtag feminism and the polyphonic nature of activist discourse. *New Media & Society*, 21(2), 507–527.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444818800242>
- Neyazi, T. A. (2020). Digital propaganda, political bots and polarized politics in India. *Asian Journal of Communication*, 30(1), 39–57. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01292986.2019.1699938>
- Papacharissi, Z., & De Fatima Oliveira, M. (2012). Affective News and Networked Publics: The Rhythms of News Storytelling on #Egypt. *Journal of Communication*, 62(2), 266–282.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2012.01630.x>
- Penney, J., & Dadas, C. (2014). (Re)Tweeting in the service of protest: Digital composition and circulation in the Occupy Wall Street movement. *New Media & Society*, 16(1), 74–90.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444813479593>
- Poell, T., & van Dijck, J. (2018). Social Media and New Protest Movements. In J. Burgess, A. Marwick, & T. Poell. (Eds.), *The SAGE Handbook of Social Media*. SAGE Publications.
- Polletta, F. (2006). *It was Like a Fever: Storytelling in Protest and Politics*. University of Chicago Press.
- Shaw, F. (2012). 'HOTTEST 100 WOMEN.' *Australian Feminist Studies*, 27(74), 373–387.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/08164649.2012.727270>
- Shaw, F. (2016). "Bitch I Said Hi": The Bye Felipe Campaign and Discursive Activism in Mobile Dating Apps. *Social Media + Society*, 2(4), 205630511667288.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2056305116672889>
- Tombleson, B., & Wolf, K. (2017). Rethinking the circuit of culture: How participatory culture has transformed cross-cultural communication. *Public Relations Review*, 43(1), 14–25.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2016.10.017>

Tufekci, Z. (2015). Algorithmic Harms beyond Facebook and Google: Emergent Challenges of Computational Agency. *Journal on Telecommunications & High Tech Law*, 13(23), 203–216.

<https://doi.org/10.1525/sp.2007.54.1.23>.

Tufekci, Z. (2017). *Twitter and Tear Gas: The Power and Fragility of Networked Protest*. Yale University Press.

Wojcieszak, M., & Smith, B. (2013). Will politics be tweeted? New media use by Iranian youth in 2011. *New Media & Society*, 16(1), 91–109. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444813479594>

Woolley, S., & Howard, P. N. (2016). Social media, revolution, and the rise of the political bot. In *Routledge handbook of media, conflict, and security*. Routledge.

Young, S. (1997). *Changing the Wor(l)d: Discourse, Politics, and the Feminist Movement*. Routledge.